

UDK 338

ANALYSIS OF CAUSAL RELATIONSHIPS OF FACTORS AFFECTING THE QUALITY OF SERVICES IN THE TOURISM SECTOR

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***Abstract.** By analyzing the factors affecting the quality of services in the tourism sector, it is possible to correctly approach the processes taking place in the tourism market and to increase the satisfaction of consumers with the quality of services and to increase the number of existing and potential customers by providing quality services to the tourist market. The analysis of factors affecting the quality of services in the tourism market in Uzbekistan is covered in this article.*

***Key words.** Tourism services market, attributes affecting the quality of transport services, consumer satisfaction with the quality of services*

Introduction. As we know, the market of tourism services is developing day by day, the competition in the tourism market is also increasing, and this causes an increase in the demand of consumers for quality products and services. Service quality has gradually been recognized as a key factor in creating an advantage in tourism by attracting and retaining customers and converting them into loyal customers in a competitive market. Tourism is a dynamic industry and cost is not the only differentiating factor. Quality is a key component for the intensity of tourism business. There are several factors that affect the quality of services in the tourism sector, including the activities of collective housing, tourism consumption, transport and other services.

Literature analysis and Methodology. One of the keys to success in the tourism services market is to focus on customer experience. Customer satisfaction, loyalty and positive word of mouth provide competitive advantage for tourism

businesses, Mariani, Di Felice. [1]. Therefore, experts emphasize the importance of providing customer-oriented services.

It is recognized that technological development plays a major role in the market of tourism services. The Internet, mobile apps, booking systems and other digital tools enable tourism businesses to be more efficient in areas such as marketing, booking and customer relationship management, Molinillo & Japutra. [2].

In recent years, the concept of sustainable tourism has gained great importance. Experts recommend adopting the principles of sustainable tourism, such as preserving natural and cultural resources, involving the local community, and reducing the impact of tourism on the environment, according to the World Tourism Organization. [3].

In the market of tourism services, there is a consensus that new markets should be constantly explored. In particular, it is recommended to evaluate the tourism potential of developing countries and develop alternative types of tourism, Davison. [4].

Results. Based on the analysis of causal relationships of factors affecting the quality of services in the field of tourism, we obtained results by analyzing the factors affecting the quality of services, which is one of the main services. According to Um, there are a number of factors that affect transport services, and they serve to improve the quality and efficiency of transport services by improving the attributes included in them (Figure 1).

Among the attributes, first of all, reliability and speed are included, and by improving these characteristics, it will be possible to increase the level of satisfaction of the users of the transport service with the service quality.

In transport services, the importance of reliability and speed is very important. People want to reach their destination safely and quickly. Therefore, any service provider must provide fast and reliable services to gain the trust of their customers.

Reliability - the ability to quickly and accurately respond to customer requests. In the transportation industry, this means that vehicles arrive on time and on their

way, and are delivered safely to customers. It is also important that transport service providers respond quickly to customer support needs.

Promptness is also important because time is precious. Especially for business trips or emergencies, customers want to reach their destination quickly. Therefore, transportation service providers must be able to provide prompt service according to the demands of their customers. Otherwise, customers will not be satisfied with their service and will look for a better service provider. As a result, being honest and prompt in transportation equipment is critical to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Therefore, transport service providers must provide fast and reliable services to gain the trust of their customers.

Transportation availability refers to how easily individuals can access and move around transportation systems, including public transportation and private transportation options. Accessibility can be affected by a number of factors, including the physical design and infrastructure of transportation systems, the availability of alternative modes of transportation, transportation costs, and the mobility level and ability of individuals. Improving access to transportation services can increase inclusion, increase individual mobility and independence, and support economic growth and development.

The impact of the safety factor on the quality of the transport service is significant. In order to provide a good transport service, first of all, it is necessary to ensure safety. For example, traffic accidents in road transport both threaten the safety of people's lives and property, and cause traffic jams and long breaks. On the other hand, plane crashes or aviation security issues in air traffic can cause major disruptions in transportation. Therefore, it is necessary to implement many measures to ensure safety in the airline industry.

There are similar safety factors in sea and rail transport. Incidents such as shipwrecks in waterways and train wrecks in rail transport can disrupt transport services. Therefore, a safe and reliable structure must be provided for the stability and quality of transport services. This is possible with measures taken by the authorities. In addition, the enterprises providing transport services are obliged to

comply with safety standards, which leads to an improvement in the safety factor and an increase in the quality of transport services.

Figure 1

¹ Developed by the author

Convenience and cheapness of transport service has a positive effect on the quality of service. Convenient and cheap transport service makes it easier for customers to use the service and causes them to value the quality of the service.

In addition, the low-cost transportation service significantly lowers the customer's demands on the quality of service, and there will be no gap between the service expected by the customer and the service provided by the service provider, even if it is in a positive direction. Also, cheap transport service is attractive to customers.

In our work, we studied the factors affecting the quality of services and analyzed their causes and consequences. First of all, the factors affecting the quality of transport services, which is the main type of service in tourism services, were studied, and in the assessment of its impact, the trend of changes in transport services in Uzbekistan in the last 5 years was assessed. (Table 1).

Table 1

Passenger transportation and passenger turnover by types of transport

Indicators	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Volume of transport services (trln sums)	44.2	54.5	53.7	67.2	81.0

Share of services by types of transport in 2022

Car transport service	Air transport	Railway transport	Auxiliary transport activity	Other types of transport activities
51%	14.2%	11.4%	10.3%	13.1%
41.31 trln sums	11.5 trln sums	9.234 trln sums	8.343 trln sums	10.61 trln sums

According to the table, in 2018, transport services amounted to 44.2 trillion sums, and in 2019, this indicator increased to 54.5 trillion sums. In 2020, when many industries began to face a crisis due to the Covid pandemic, the amount of income in transport services also began to fall, and at the end of the year this figure was 53.7 billion sums. In 2021, the reforms carried out by our state to improve the quality of services began to bear fruit, and the indicator of transport services amounted to 67.2 trillion sums. In 2022, the indicator of transport services amounted to 81 trillion sums.

If we look at the share of transport types in 2022, motor transport service in Uzbekistan is considered the leader compared to other types of services and made up 51% of the entire transport service (41.31 trillion sums).

Summary. In the analysis of factors affecting the quality of services in the field of tourism, we studied transport services, which are one of the main services, and the role of this service in improving the quality of services in the development of the tourist market of Uzbekistan is gaining its own importance. A number of decisions and decrees have been adopted to develop transport services and improve their quality in our country, and these actions are actually reflected in the numbers.

In the near future, we can see the practical effect of large-scale reforms and investment programs implemented in the transport sector of our country, providing all sectors of the economy with quality and competitive logistics and transport services. and all sections of the population, as well as the significant contribution of this sector to the development of the transport industry.

The analysis of the characteristics of the development of entrepreneurship in the field of service and service in our country allows to distinguish the directions of the need for the development of small and medium forms of entrepreneurship in the field of service, which are important for our national economy. economy.

The development of small and private forms of business activity in the service sector, unlike other sectors of the economy, is explained by the lack of labor force and the need for relatively small capital investments in the initial

stages. It is characterized by quick adaptation to changing business conditions, simplicity of the management system, sensitivity to changes in the type of activity as a reaction to changes in the market situation, and good knowledge of the level of demand for a certain service in a certain market. and others.

At the same time, special attention should be paid to the system of state support for small and medium-sized businesses in the service sector.

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